

RESEARCH HOTSPOTS AND FRONTIER EVOLUTION OF CHINA DATA PUBLISHING FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF DATA ELEMENT EMPOWERMENT —A VISUALIZED BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS BASED ON CITESPACE

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Abstract

In recent years, with the continuous advancement of science and technology and the progression of the digital era, data publishing has emerged as a hot topic in the publishing field, with significant growth in related research. To illustrate the current status, development, and trends in data publishing research, this paper employs a combined methodology of scientometrics and scientific knowledge graph analysis based on literature analysis. Utilizing CiteSpace software for data processing and analysis of data publishing literature samples, it summarizes key research topics across different stages of data publishing. The study explores the developmental trends and dynamic directions of data publishing as a frontier business model within the publishing industry, aiming to provide theoretical references and insights for further research in this field.

Keywords: Data Publishing; Scientific Data Publishing; Big Data Publishing; Data Elements; Publishing Data; Knowledge Graph; CiteSpace.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, with the acceleration of digitalization and the elevated strategic status of data elements, data publishing as an innovative model of deep integration within the publishing industry has gradually shifted from digital intelligence technology empowerment to the restructuring of production factors. It has become a vital engine driving academic exchange and industrial transformation.

Driven by policies such as the "Opinions on Establishing a Data Foundation System to Better Leverage the Role of Data Elements" and the "Three-Year Action Plan for 'Data Element ×' (2024–2026)," data publishing research has exhibited interdisciplinary convergence.

Its theoretical scope has transcended traditional publishing boundaries, and its research paradigm has undergone phased transitions—"resource openness—technology-driven—element activation"—becoming a frontier field in publishing studies, information science, computer science.

Against this backdrop, systematically mapping the knowledge framework of domestic data publishing research not only helps to comprehensively grasp the development history and

paradigm shifts but also provides systematic references for the deep integration of enabling into data elements the publishing industry.

Based on this, this paper takes 238 articles from China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) between 2010 and 2025 as samples, and uses the CiteSpace visualization tool to analyze the research hotspots and dynamic trends in data publishing, focusing on three dimensions: first, systematically outlining the research hotspots and core issues in the data publishing field during different periods from 2010 to 2025; second, analyzing the differentiated research paths and knowledge connections between scientific data publishing, big data publishing, and data publishing; third, predicting future research directions and clarifying key issues such as data publishing policies, assetization, governance systems, and talent cultivation, thereby providing support for constructing a theoretical framework and practical pathways for data publishing.

DATA SOURCES AND RESEARCH METHODS

1. Data Sources

The sample data for this study was sourced from the China National Knowledge Infrastructure (CNKI) academic journal database. Using advanced search methods with the query "Subject: Data Publishing" OR "Subject: Publishing Data Elements," retrieved on March 6, 2025, a total of 1,306 academic journal articles were identified.

After data cleaning to exclude non-research literature such as news publicity and column introductions, as well as irrelevant documents, the final data sample comprised 238 articles. The time span covered articles from 2010 to 2025 (Note: Data download completed on February 17, 2025). Valid literature was exported in RefWorks format and converted into actionable data entries using CiteSpace software (version 6.4.R1).

Table 1: Literature Search Parameters and Content

Search Parameter Settings	Search Content and Results
Database	CNKI
Journal Sources	EI, Peking University Core, CSSCI, CSCD, AMI, WJCI
Search Method	(Subject = "Data Publishing") OR (Subject = "Publishing Data Elements")
Time Span	September 28, 2010 to February 17, 2025 (Search conducted on March 6, 2025)
Search Results	238

2. Research Methods

This study integrates qualitative and quantitative research methods, comprehensively employing literature analysis, scientometrics, and scientific knowledge graph analysis. Literature analysis systematically collects and organizes existing literature to obtain research information.

Scientometrics, based on mathematical and statistical principles, uses the external characteristics of scientific literature as its research object to quantitatively describe, evaluate, and predict the current status and trends of scientific and technological development.^[1]

Scientific knowledge map analysis employs data mining, information processing, knowledge metrology, and graph visualization^[2] to visually represent knowledge characteristics and interconnections, intuitively showcasing disciplinary frontiers and developmental trajectories. The organic integration of these three approaches transforms extensive research outputs into statistical analyses of word frequency, co-occurrence, and citation relationships.

By constructing scientific knowledge graphs across various categories and conducting systematic analysis and synthesis based on literature themes, this methodology better accommodates the specialized and comprehensive trends in data publishing research, comprehensively presenting research themes and developmental trajectories.

3. Analytical Tools

This study employs CiteSpace analysis software developed by Professor Chao Mei Chen's team at Drexel University to conduct multidimensional analysis: First, it visually presents fundamental metrics such as annual publication volume, journal publication volume, author distribution, and institutional distribution to grasp the overall landscape and interrelationships within the data publishing research field.

Second, it generates keyword co-occurrence maps to identify high-frequency keywords and clarify core research themes. Third, it generates clustering label maps and research cluster summary tables to identify core thematic domains, tracing hot topics and frontier focuses across different developmental stages. Fourth, it detects keyword mutation rates to explore future trends and delineate subsequent research directions.

ANALYSIS OF HOT TOPICS IN DATA PUBLISHING RESEARCH

The analysis of core issues in data publishing primarily relies on keyword co-occurrence maps and cluster label maps to summarize key terms and focal topics in data publishing research, thereby capturing its cutting-edge dynamics and hotspots.

1. Keyword Co-occurrence and Cluster Label Map Analysis

(1) Keyword Co-occurrence Map Analysis: Keywords serve as pivotal terms in academic research, and co-occurrence networks reveal thematic affinities.^[3] Higher co-occurrence frequencies and greater network density indicate stronger relevance within the field and closer thematic connections.

The co-occurrence map constructed for data publishing research in this study (see Figure 1 below) comprises 233 keywords and 611 network connections, with a network density of 0.0226.

Figure 1: Keyword Co-occurrence Map for Data Publishing Research

As shown in the figure above, the core keywords in the "data publishing" research from 2010 to 2025 include "data publishing", "big data", "digital publishing", "scientific data", "data element", "data sharing", "publishing", "data journal", "data paper", and "publishing industry". To further analyze the frequency, centrality, and annual distribution of these keywords, this study has compiled a list of high-frequency keywords in data publishing research (see Table 2).

Table 2: High-Frequency Keywords in Data Publishing Research

No.	Keyword	Frequency	Centrality	Year of First Appearance
1	Data Publishing	65	0.52	2013
2	Big Data	50	0.75	2013
3	Digital Publishing	39	0.35	2013
4	Scientific Data	35	0.16	2014
5	Data Elements	19	0.12	2023
6	Data Sharing	15	0.01	2010
7	Publication	13	0.07	2013
8	Data Journals	12	0.01	2015
9	Data Papers	12	0.01	2015
10	Publishing Industry	9	0.07	2015
11	Publishing Data	8	0.05	2016
12	Intelligent Publishing	7	0.02	2019
13	Open Science	6	0.02	2018
14	Book Publishing	6	0.03	2021
15	Digitalization	6	0.03	2015

No.	Keyword	Frequency	Centrality	Year of First Appearance
16	Data Assets	6	0.03	2014
17	Knowledge Services	5	0.04	2015
18	Production Factors	5	0.02	2024
19	Data Security	4	0.03	2023
20	Academic Publishing	3	0.02	2018

The table 2 reveals that the top three keywords by frequency and centrality are "data publishing" (65,0.52), "big data" (50,0.75), and "digital publishing" (39,0.35), highlighting the research focus. From a temporal perspective, the earliest appearing keywords were "data sharing" (2010), "data citation" (2010), and "metadata" (2011), indicating that scientific data publishing under the backdrop of open data sharing was a core focus in early research. The mid-phase centered on keywords like "digitization" (2015), "publishing data" (2016), and "intelligent publishing" (2019), highlighting a research orientation empowered by big data technologies. The emergence of keywords such as "data elements" (2023) and "data security" (2023) in the later phase confirms that data publishing, viewed through the lens of production factors has become the current research focus in the publishing industry.

(2) Cluster Label Map Analysis:

Figure 2: Keyword Contribution Cluster Map for Data Publishing Research

Cluster analysis generates a cluster label map based on keyword similarity features. A cluster module value (Q-value) > 0.3 indicates a significant cluster structure, while an average silhouette value (S-value) > 0.7 signifies reliable clustering results.^[4] The clustering label map generated by this graduate student (see Figure 2) has a Q-value of approximately 0.65 > 0.3, indicating significant clustering effectiveness; The S-value of approximately 0.88 > 0.7 indicates the clustering results are persuasive. After removing redundant clusters related to "data publishing," it is evident that research on data publishing in China primarily revolves around the following themes: #1 Publishing, #2 Digital Publishing, #3 Data Elements, #4 Intelligence, #5 Publishing Industry, #6 Book Publishing, #7 University Publishing, and #8 New Quality Productive Forces. To further investigate the publication volume, distribution time, and key research keywords of different clustering labels, a cluster summary table was generated, as shown in Table 3 below:

Table 3: Research Cluster Summary

Cluster ID, Name	Cluster Size	Cluster ID	Average Publication Year	LLR Log-Likelihood Label Value Top Keyword
#0 Data Publishing	58	0.92	2017	Data Publishing (28.1, 1.0E-4); Scientific Data (26.9, 1.0E-4); Big Data (22.57, 1.0E-4); Data Papers (20, 1.0E-4); Data Journals (20, 1.0E-4)
#1 Publishing	42	0.958	2016	Publishing (22.85, 1.0E-4); Big Data (18.25, 1.0E-4); Data Publishing (10.85, 0.001); Publishing Enterprises (9.42, 0.005); Digital Publishing (6.8, 0.01)
#2 Digital Publishing	34	0.865	2018	Digital Publishing (20.23, 1.0E-4); Smart Publishing (10.37, 0.005); Artificial Intelligence (10.37, 0.005); Data Publishing (9.13, 0.005); Industry Chain (6.88, 0.01)
#3 Data Elements	21	0.837	2023	Digital Publishing (20.23, 1.0E-4); Intelligent Publishing (10.37, 0.005); Artificial Intelligence (10.37, 0.005); Data Publishing (9.13, 0.005); Industrial Chain (6.88, 0.01)
#4 Intelligence	20	0.895	2017	Intelligence (11.21, 0.001); Academic Publishing (11.21, 0.001); Digitization (7.52, 0.01); Open Access (5.56, 0.05); Publishing Convergence (5.56, 0.05)
#5 Publishing Industry	13	0.956	2018	Intelligence (11.21, 0.001); Academic Publishing (11.21, 0.001); Digitization (7.52, 0.01); Open Access (5.56, 0.05); Publishing Convergence (5.56, 0.05)
#6 Book Publishing	12	0.939	2021	Book Publishing (14.41, 0.001); Considerations (7.1, 0.01); Personalization (7.1, 0.01); Premiumization (7.1, 0.01); Application Cases (7.1, 0.01)
#7 University Publishing	3	0.992	2019	University Publishing (9.1, 0.005); Challenges (9.1, 0.005); Opportunities (9.1, 0.005); Data Publishing (1.36, 0.5); Big Data (0.66, 0.5)
#8 New Quality Productive Forces	3	0.989	2021	Ecosystem (9.1, 0.005); Intelligent Publishing (9.1, 0.005); Innovative Development (9.1, 0.005); New Quality Productive Forces (5.32, 0.05); Big Data (0.66, 0.5)

The table above reveals that current research hotspots in China's data publishing field primarily focus on: 1. Science data publishing research centered on open sharing, encompassing cluster #0 Data Publishing and #7 University Publishing, with keywords including "scientific data" (26.9, 1.0E-4), "big data" (22.57,1.0E-4), "data papers" (20,1.0E-4), "data journals" (20,1.0E-4), and "university publishing" (9.1, 0.005). Universities have become key players in data publishing practices during this phase, where open attributes present both challenges and opportunities. 2. Technology-driven big data publishing research, covering cluster #1 Publishing, #2 Digital Publishing and #4 Intelligence with keywords such as "publishing enterprises" (9.42,0.005), "intelligent publishing" (10.37,0.005), "artificial intelligence" (10.37,0.005), and "Intelligence" (11.21,0.001). Publishing enterprises are leveraging big data technologies to optimize publishing activities, restructure the "industry chain," and promote the development of "publishing convergence." 3. Data-driven publishing research focusing on production factors, including cluster #3 Data Elements and #8 New Quality Productive Forces, with keywords such as "digital publishing" (20.23,1.0E-4), "ecosystem" (9.1, 0.005), and "intelligent publishing" (9.1, 0.005). This phase represents the deep integration of data elements into publishing, driving the industry's digital transformation and empowering high-quality development.

2. Analysis of Hot Topics in Data Publishing Research

The evolution of data publishing reflects a paradigm shift from "data resource openness" to "data value release". This paper conducts a detailed analysis through three core research dimensions: 1) scientific data publishing studies emphasizing open sharing, 2) big data publishing research driven by technological innovation, and 3) data publishing studies oriented toward production factors. These three dimensions address distinct developmental needs at different stages, collectively forming the research framework for China's data publishing landscape.

2.1 Scientific Data Publishing: Open Access and Sharing

Cluster #0 Data Publishing and Cluster #7 University Publishing fall under the scientific data publishing category, encompassing keywords such as "scientific data," "data sharing," and "open science," with a total of 61 related publications. After introducing the concept of scientific data publishing from abroad, China has driven open science policies through technological support such as data association technology, digital object unique identifier (DOI), data platform architecture, and platform development. The goal is to "achieve open sharing, reusability, and value realization of research data through standardized management and sharing mechanisms, thereby promoting open science development".^[5] Scientific data publishing has become a focal point in academia, publishing circles, and industries. Current research on scientific data publishing primarily focuses on four aspects: theoretical connotation, subject-object relationships, publishing models, and workflow, with relatively abundant research outcomes.

First, the theoretical framework of scientific data publishing is examined from two perspectives: "scientific data publishing adhering to traditional publishing principles"

and "data dissemination grounded in the open spirit of the internet."^[6] The former retains the core characteristics of traditional academic publishing, emphasizing services such as storage, management, mining, and sharing of scientific data. The latter incorporates internet-based data sharing practices into the realm of data publishing, establishing internet-centric data publishing. Researchers adopting this perspective demonstrate an inclusive approach to defining data publishing, with its core principle being the reduction of mandatory requirements for traditional processes like peer review and editorial refinement, prioritizing instead data accessibility and dissemination efficiency as primary evaluation criteria.

Second, research on the subject-object dynamics of scientific data publishing primarily focuses on scholars such as Li Xiaoyan^[7], Zhang Lili^[8], and Chen Ming^[9]. These studies argue that the primary actors in scientific data publishing are the diverse stakeholders engaged in research data openness activities, including governments, public service institutions, researchers, and the general public. The subject matter encompasses scientific data itself and its derivative information. As the top-level regulatory body, the government formulates data publishing policies, establishes legal frameworks, and standardizes principles and usage scopes for data object accessibility. Within public service institutions, university publishing entities fulfill three roles: infrastructure providers, quality gatekeepers, and open science advocates. Researchers simultaneously embody both producer and user attributes, serving as dual-role actors in data ecosystems. The general public, as end-users, participates in scientific governance through data utilization, thereby realizing the value of the data itself. Research in this phase has primarily focused on academic contexts while underexploiting data's commercial potential, facing challenges including high long-term preservation costs, data privacy risks, and quality oversight issues.

Third, regarding the publication models of scientific data, He Lin et al.^[10] categorized data publishing into three types based on publishing methods: "data warehousing, institutional repositories, and journal self-publishing." Zhang Xiaolin et al.^[11] classified data publishing according to content into "data release as supplementary material to papers, independent data publishing, and data papers." Zhang Xiaoqiang et al.^[12] divided models by publishing entities 'control over information flow into "publishing institution control model, independent control model by non-publishing entities, hybrid model, and 'secondary' publishing model." Zhang Lili^[13] categorized data publishing by its relationship with papers into "data attached to publications, independent data publishing, and data center data publishing." Zhang Jingbei et al.^[14] classified data publishing by independence and presentation methods into "independent data publishing, data paper publishing^[15] collaborative publishing, and journal self-publishing." Huang Guobin et al.^[16] proposed two models—integrated publishing and independent publishing—based on the generation scenarios of scientific data.

Fourth, the workflow of scientific data publication may vary in practice due to differences in entities, formats, policies and platforms, resulting in distinct characteristics. In 2018, the "Several Opinions on Further Strengthening the Construction of Scientific Research Integrity"^[17] explicitly required universities and research institutions to advance the

development of professional data publishing platforms and standardize data management processes through FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Wu Lizong et al.^[18] proposed a general data publication workflow comprising five stages: "data release, peer review, data publication and permanent storage, data citation, and data evaluation." Qu Baoqiang et al.^[19] After reviewing major domestic and international data publishing platforms and data journal publishing practices, summarized the data publishing process as comprising five steps: "data storage, data description, data management, data identification, and data publication"; Xu Jie et al.^[20] proposed that "the general process of data publishing includes five fundamental stages: data submission, data storage, data review, data citation, and data evaluation."

2.2 Big Data Publishing: Technology-Driven

Cluster #1 Publishing, #2 Digital Publishing, and #4 Intelligence form the Big Data Publishing theme, encompassing keywords such as "big data," "publishing enterprises," "artificial intelligence," and "publishing industry chain," with a cluster size of 96 articles. Since 2013, big data technology has empowered development across industries, giving rise to the concept of "big data publishing." Centered on the "publishing + big data" paradigm, research has focused on four key areas: conceptual definition, data resource classification, data construction processes, and industry empowerment. The aim is to leverage big data technology to accurately reflect, guide, and optimize publishing-related activities, thereby enhancing publishing efficiency and driving the digital transformation of the publishing industry.

First, regarding the conceptual essence of big data publishing: In 2015, Han Li^[21] proposed that "big data publishing is a model for advancing the publishing industry through data integration and computation"; in 2016, Shi Yongqin et al.^[22] stated: "The core of big data publishing lies in leveraging data analysis to enhance publishing effectiveness and reduce costs." In 2017, Mark J.H. Freitas et al.^[23] proposed: "Big data publishing involves reconstructing publishing workflows based on the collection, analysis, and application of massive datasets to achieve intelligent, personalized, and precise content production, dissemination, and services."

Second, the data resources in big data publishing are primarily categorized into "content data, user data, and interaction data"^[24] Content data exhibits greater modernity, openness, and interactivity compared to traditional publishing^[25]. User data is further subdivided into "type data, commonality data, and individuality data," enabling precise characterization of user traits. Interaction data, driven by big data technologies, deepens publishing interactivity.

Third, big data publishing centers its data construction around the core process of "data collection, indexing, computation, modeling, and service."^[26] Data collection integrates content data, market data, and user data, serving as the resource foundation for big data applications^[27]; Following massive data collection, indexing is performed on the acquired data; post-indexing data is processed using a combination of cloud computing and statistical analysis to identify optimal computational solutions; data models are constructed to address personalized user needs by integrating different disciplinary systems and industry applications;

finally, a data service system is designed based on the entire data workflow, comprehensively driving the transformation of publishing from content publishing to knowledge services.

Fourth, big data's empowerment of the publishing industry primarily focuses on leveraging big data technologies to: uncover user needs, optimize topic planning, enhance content quality, innovate product formats, update marketing models, transform business processes, and drive the publishing industry's transition toward data-driven and intelligent operations. Zhang Zhenyu and Zhou Li^[28] have noted that "big data publishing, through technological integration and model innovation, propels the industry from unidirectional dissemination toward a multidimensional interactive ecosystem." In content creation, generative AI is applied to topic planning, text generation, and multimodal content development, enriching publishing product diversity. Product formats see rapid growth in digital offerings like e-books and online literature. Marketing models adopt user-demand-driven approaches, delivering customized services and optimized consumption experiences. Meanwhile, traditional editors as publishing professionals are evolving into digital editors and versatile talents.

Based on the above, big data has significantly empowered publishing activities, providing a solid foundation and crucial support for the digital transformation and media convergence of traditional publishing. However, this phase still faces ethical challenges such as user privacy breaches, content homogenization, and algorithmic bias. The copyright ownership of AI-generated content remains ambiguous, and data application often remains at the process optimization level, lacking systematic exploration of the value of data elements.

2.3 Data Publishing: Element Activation

Cluster #3 Data Elements and #8 New Quality Productive Forces focus on data-driven publishing, encompassing keywords like "data classification," "data governance," and "deep integration in publishing." This cluster comprises 24 articles. The release of the "Three-Year Action Plan for Data Element × (2024–2026)" marks China's entry into the market-oriented phase of data publishing. Its core objective is to unlock the value of publishing data through technologies like AIGC and blockchain, leveraging the multiplier effect and infinite penetration of data to achieve the publishing industry's "four-in-one"^[29] value system. Research hotspots in this phase focus on the conceptual framework of data publishing, data classification and grading, fundamental processes and workflows, data development and utilization, management services, and security protection.

First, regarding the conceptual definition of data publishing, Zhang Xinxin proposed in 2015: "Data publishing utilizes data as a production factor, treating text, images, audio, video, and other content as data representations. It centers publishing activities around key processes such as data mining, collection, and indexing. By constructing data models, it ultimately achieves the implementation of data applications and services."^[30] In 2024, he further elaborated: "As the core production resource of the publishing industry in the digital era, publishing data elements fundamentally involve the structured integration of three types of data—content, users, and interactions—to form a new type of production factor that is

quantifiable, transferable, and capable of value appreciation."^[31] Compared to traditional production factors, data elements possess unique attributes of exclusivity, reusability, and increasing returns to scale.

Second, regarding data classification and categorization, publishing data can be divided from various perspectives and dimensions into: line data and block data; personal data and non-personal data; public data and social data; external publishing data and internal data; professional publishing data, educational publishing data, and mass publishing data; content data, user data, interaction data, and governance data.^[32] Based on this classification, data can be further categorized by importance and risk level into "core publishing data, important publishing data, and general publishing data".^[33]

Third, the fundamental stages and processes of data publishing encompass seven key phases: collection, storage, utilization, processing, transmission, provision, and disclosure.^[34] This framework facilitates the transformation of raw publishing data into processed data resources, which are then integrated into production and operational management processes to become data elements and data products. Ultimately, these enter the data circulation phase to form data assets.

Fourth, research on data utilization primarily focuses on advancing the digitization, productization, and assetization of publishing resources to fully unlock the value of publishing data elements: First, raw publishing data undergoes the "seven-step method"^[35] for publishing data construction, transforming it into usable, digitally formatted publishing data resources. Second, after undergoing foundational processes like "data collection, storage, and processing", new data is formed, signifying the completion of publishing data productization. Cai Fei^[36] and Bian Kaixing^[37], among others, focus on publishing data assetization research, proposing: "The process of advancing from data resourceization to assetization involves transforming abstract data into corporate assets and economic benefits, achieving controllable, profitable, and measurable publishing data." Li Jingyi et al.^[38] adopting a publishing enterprise data asset management perspective, propose effective strategies for advancing publishing data assetization centered on four key aspects: "data governance, data inclusion in financial statements, data circulation, and data product innovation." Zhang Xinxin^[35] further emphasizes: "Promoting data inclusion in financial statements is a critical step in forming a closed-loop process of data resourceization, resource productization, product assetization, and data capitalization. It is the core step for value release, requiring the establishment of data rights confirmation, pricing, and trading mechanisms. Utilizing hybrid valuation models to address accounting measurement challenges will drive the transformation of data from resources into commodities."

Fifth, Data Management Services and Security Protection: The expansion of data scale and enhancement of data value have increased the difficulty of data security and privacy protection. Data security has become the most urgent and fundamental issue in the digital economy era. To address this challenge, China released the "Data Security Governance White Paper 6.0" in 2024^[39] innovatively proposing governance approaches such as personal information protection, data risk assessment, data security certification, data security review,

and scenario-based control. Jiang Yu ^[40] proposed clarifying data security standards and operational norms, vigorously developing monitoring technologies such as database encryption and data de-identification, and following a four-pronged governance approach: "institutional support—transaction systems—market regulation—technological empowerment." Meanwhile, the author of this paper previously recommended accelerating the training of data security officers and governance specialists within data publishing entities to safeguard data openness and collaboration. Driven by both policy and technology, research treating data as a key production factor continues to emerge. Existing studies have preliminarily established a theoretical and practical framework for data publishing research across three dimensions: foundational theory, applied theory, and theoretical practice. However, the field currently faces challenges including weak data concepts, lagging legal frameworks for rights confirmation, and an incomplete standardization system, necessitating sustained and in-depth follow-up research.

3. Analysis of Dynamic Trends in Data Publishing Research

This paper examines the frontiers of data publishing research through timeline maps and emergent word analysis to precisely capture its dynamic trajectory. On one hand, timeline maps clearly display the start and end times, span, time zone distribution, and hotspots of keywords, helping to clarify the connections and differentiation of research themes, as well as their evolutionary relationships over time. This facilitates mapping the evolution of each subfield and predicting future research trends.

Figure 3: Keyword Clustering Temporal Map of Data Publishing Research

The domestic data publishing timeline view generated by Cite Space software (see Figure 3) displays keywords in chronological order from left to right and diminishing clustering information from top to bottom. Arc lengths correspond to temporal spans, enabling clear identification of research hotspots' inception points and evolutionary trajectories.

On the other hand, we constructed a keyword prominence map. Through word frequency analysis, we identified keywords with significant frequency fluctuations during specific periods, thereby clarifying the distribution of research frontiers, trending shifts, and latest developments. Using CiteSpace for keyword prominence analysis, we obtained a prominence map containing 25 prominent keywords, including their burst times, intensity, and development trends (see Figure 4).

Figure 4: Distribution of Emergence Intensity and Timing for Keywords in Data Publishing Research

Analysis of research data over the past 15 years in Figures 3 and 4 reveals that domestic data publishing research has generally followed an evolutionary path of "data resources—data assets—data ecosystem."

Phase I (2010–2015): Research began with "data citation," "data sharing," and "metadata" as logical starting points, gradually expanding to core topics such as "scientific data publishing," "digital publishing," and "scientific data." This phase focused on defining foundational concepts for scientific data publishing and constructing management systems for scientific data. During this period, the key core terms were metadata (1.36), data sharing (2.03), and data journals (1.21). Notably, the emergence of "metadata" in 2011 signaled the commencement of standardized scientific data management. In 2014, the "Guiding Opinions on Scientific Data Management" was released, clarifying requirements for open access to research data and promoting the establishment of data journals. Concurrently, key issues in the publishing process such as "intellectual property rights" and "peer review" entered the public research discourse, laying a theoretical foundation for subsequent studies and highlighting China's initial explorations in scientific data publishing.

Phase II (2015–2020): Data publishing research expanded in both disciplinary convergence and practical application. On one hand, studies advancing the scientific data publishing paradigm exhibited interdisciplinary characteristics. Against the backdrop of "open science" and "data open," they delved into topics like "data journals," "data papers," and "scientific journals," while exploring issues such as "data review" and "data storage" to drive innovation in data publishing content and quality control. On the other hand, the 2015 Action Plan for Promoting Big Data Development spurred the integration of big data with the publishing industry, giving rise to research on "big data publishing." The research perspective shifted toward the publishing industry ecosystem, Big data (2.36) and user data (1.17) emerged as core keywords, while topics like "publishing enterprises" and "precision marketing" gained prominence. Research prioritized exploring innovative data analysis strategies and application models for the publishing industry in the big data era, driving data publishing studies from conceptual frameworks toward practical implementation.

Phase III (2020–Present): As data solidified its status as a key production factor, its driving role gradually emerged across industries. Data publishing research closely aligned with unlocking data value and meeting innovation demands in the publishing sector. Core themes of this phase included "data elements," "data governance," and "digital economy," while keywords like scientific data (2.31) and data policy (1.31) also attracted significant attention. This phase centers on data as a core production factor, exploring pathways for data assetization under national data strategies, developing data products and services, and building supporting ecosystems to drive innovation within the publishing industry system. Concurrently, research on scientific data publishing deepened under the empowerment of data elements, yielding steady growth in outcomes. Furthermore, technologies like "Intelligence" and "media convergence" fostered new productive forces in publishing, accelerating its integrated development. This phase demonstrates that China's data publishing research has evolved from

a single-dimensional approach toward a synergistic ecosystem integrating "policy-technology-industry."

In summary, over the past fifteen years, domestic data publishing research has achieved a leap from foundational concept development to in-depth exploration of key elements, and from fragmented experimentation to systematic advancement. This evolutionary journey reveals that in the era of digitalization and data-driven transformation, policy direction, technological innovation, and industrial demand profoundly shape the research priorities and trends within data publishing.

In the future, driven by both policy and technology, research priorities may focus on data publishing policies, publishing data elements, publishing data assets, data publishing talent, and data governance. First, China's data publishing policy research should revolve around the "Twenty Data Measures," the "Three-Year Action Plan for Data Element × (2024–2026)," and the publishing sector's 15th Five-Year Plan. It should expedite the introduction of targeted publishing industry policies, explore legal issues arising from data as a production factor, protect the cultural, commercial, ideological value, and personal privacy security of publishing data, and improve institutional safeguards for publishing data security. Second, the "Three-Year Action Plan for Data Element × (2024–2026)" states that "data elements possess amplifying, synergistic, and multiplicative effects; their multiplier effect must be fully leveraged to empower economic and social development." Research on publishing data elements should delve into its theoretical implications, uncover the underlying logic of how publishing data elements empower value creation in the publishing industry, and emphasize the enabling role of data elements in publishing activities along with practical implementation pathways. Third, research on publishing data assets can explore pathways for transforming data into resources, products, and assets based on documents such as the Interim Provisions on Accounting Treatment of Enterprise Data Resources and the Guiding Opinions on Strengthening Data Asset Management. It should address practical challenges by focusing on defining ownership rights for data assets on balance sheets, quality management, value assessment, establishing compliance review mechanisms, and refining information disclosure standards. Fourth, building a publishing talent pool remains a top priority during the 15th Five-Year Plan period. The digital intelligence era demands professionals proficient in data technologies. Research on data publishing editors should focus on documents such as the Opinions on Strengthening and Improving Publishing Work, the Implementation Opinions on Promoting the Joint Development of Publishing Disciplines, and the Regulations on Continuing Education for Publishing Professionals. This includes studying editorial systems and mechanisms, training models for multidisciplinary talent, curriculum development for publishing disciplines in higher education, continuing education training systems, and domestic and international experiences in data editing. Fifth, data governance serves as a key driver for advancing high-quality data publishing. Research in this field can be grounded in theories of data value chains, data lifecycle management, and asset lifecycle management. It should explore areas such as data cleansing and standardization, governance frameworks, data storage systems, data classification systems, and the development of open data governance ecosystems across industries, thereby enhancing the modernization of industry governance capabilities.

CONCLUSION

The research on data publishing has been developing continuously with the digitalization process and the deepening of data element strategy, forming a multi-dimensional evolution context with multiple topics. This paper uses Citespace software to sort out the domestic data publishing literature, and summarizes the basic situation, hot topics and dynamic trends of domestic data publishing research.

From a fundamental perspective, current research has achieved phased results with steady growth in annual publications and sustained focus on core issues, yet remains in its initial exploratory stage. Numerous unresolved problems persist in both theoretical and practical dimensions, requiring collaborative efforts between academia and industry to deepen research. Regarding research hotspots, domestic data publishing studies have formed three core thematic systems: scientific data publishing with strong open attributes centered on "scientific data" and "data sharing"; big data publishing research highlighting technological empowerment through "big data," "artificial intelligence," and "industry chains"; and data publishing research with data attributes focusing on "data elements," "data assets," and "new quality productive forces." These three categories correspond to evolutionary logic of resource openness, technology-driven development, and element activation, collectively forming a comprehensive thematic framework for data publishing research. In terms of developmental trajectory, domestic data publishing research has undergone fifteen years of evolution, achieving a profound leap from "data resources" to "data assets" and ultimately to "data ecosystems." Early efforts concentrated on standardized management and open sharing of scientific data, mid-period shifts toward integrated applications of big data technologies and publishing industries, while current research focuses on market-oriented data elements and cultivation of new quality productive forces. This reflects the publishing industry's intrinsic need to transition from content production to knowledge services and value creation, completing the evolution from basic conceptual construction to in-depth element exploration, and from fragmented individual explorations to systematic development.

Data publishing represents a new phase in digital publishing development and stands as a core research domain within the digital economy. This paper employs knowledge graph visualization methods to clarify current research status and outline academic evolution trajectories, providing references for theoretical framework construction and innovative practical approaches in this field. However, existing limitations include: 1) literature samples derived solely from CNKI database, excluding foreign-language and gray literature, which could be expanded to enhance conclusions; 2) inconsistent keyword definitions among scholars potentially affecting analysis results; 3) insufficient in-depth qualitative analysis of research hotspots, where future studies could integrate case studies and empirical analyses to further explore application models and value realization pathways of data publishing across different scenarios. As a cutting-edge industry in publishing, data publishing holds tremendous potential. Academic communities should deepen theoretical exploration and innovate practical approaches to empower publishing innovation, advance modern publishing governance, and facilitate high-quality development of the publishing sector.

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